

Pimpri Chinchwad Education Trust's
**PIMPRI CHINCHWAD COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING &
RESEARCH**

Laxminagar, Ravet, Pune – 412101

: Lab Manual :

APPLIED THERMODYNAMICS

SE Mechanical Engineering 2015 Pattern (Semester – IV)

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PIMPRI CHINCHWAD EDUCATION TRUST'S
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To be a Premier Institute of Technical Education and Research to serve the need of society and all the stakeholders.

MISSION:

To establish state-of-the-art facilities to create an environment resulting in individuals who are technically sound having professionalism, research and innovative aptitude with high moral and ethical values.

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Expt. No. :

Title of Experiment : Study of Carburetor.

Aim : To study carburetion process, Simple Carburetor and its different parts, various types of carburetor compensating devices.

Introduction :

The process of formation of a combustible fuel-air mixture by mixing the proper amount of fuel with air before admission to engine cylinder is called carburetion.

The device which supplies the mixture of correct amount of fuel and air for the efficient combustion in cylinder at all operating conditions is called Carburetor.

Air-Fuel Mixtures : Air and fuel are mixed to form three different types of mixtures,

1. Chemically Correct (Stoichiometric) Mixture –

Chemically correct or stoichiometric mixture is one in which there is just enough air (oxygen) for complete combustion of the fuel. Thus with this mixture there is complete combustion of fuel and all carbon in the fuel is converted to carbon dioxides (CO_2) and all hydrogen to water vapors (H_2O) and there is no excess oxygen remains in combustion gases.

Chemically correct (stoichiometric) Air-Fuel mixture contains about 15 part of air by mass for 1 part of octane fuel. $A : F = 15 : 1$

2. Rich Mixture –

A mixture which contains less air than the stoichiometric requirement is called a rich mixture. Thus with this mixture there is always incomplete combustion of fuel take place and all carbon can not converted to carbon dioxides (CO_2) due to deficiency of oxygen, some carbon converted to carbon monoxide (CO).

It should be noted that there is extreme limit for richness beyond which mixture unable to burn due to lack of oxygen (air) comparatively fuel in the mixture. Thus rich mixture ranges the ratio of air-fuel, from 15:1 to 9:1, beyond 9:1 mixture becomes too rich to burn.

3. Lean Mixture –

A mixture which contains excess air than the stoichiometric requirement is called a lean mixture. Thus with this mixture there is always excess oxygen with result into complete combustion of fuel and all carbon converted into carbon dioxides but excess oxygen remain in the combustion gases as it is.

A mixture which contains excess air than the stoichiometric requirement is called a lean mixture. There is also a extreme limit for leanness beyond which mixture unable to burn due to lack of fuel comparatively oxygen (air) in the mixture. Thus lean mixture ranges the ratio of air-fuel, from 15:1 to 19:1, beyond 19:1 mixture becomes too lean to burn.

Simple Carburetor :

1. Main metering & Idling system / Choke system –

Engine required rich mixture at idling and low speed, due to cold condition of engine, which is fulfilled by incorporating idling system which contains choke valve, idling air bleed, and idling jet with adjustment screw, as shown in figure below,

This system get operational at starting, idling and very low speed running of the engine and it become non-operational when throttle is opened beyond 15%.

When at starting, choke is partly closed, the very small quantity of air creases very little pressure depression at the throat of the venturi, and that is not enough to suck any fuel from the main jet.

But very low pressure caused on the downstream side of the throttle valve, the fuel rise in the idling tube and very small amount of air from the idling air bleed discharged through idling jet which mixes with venturi air and form rich mixture.

Thus the rich mixture below throttle valve is available for starting the engine. The desired air-fuel ration for idling can be regulated by idling adjustment screw.

When the throttle valve opens more than 15% the suction pressure at the idle jet is not sufficient to draw the fuel through the idling passage, thus it becomes non-operational. Thereafter of more than 15% opening of throttle valve, main air flow increases and the cruising range of operation is established.

2. Power enrichment (Economizer) system –

At the maximum power range of operation from 80% to 100% load, richer air-fuel mixture is required. An economizer / power enrichment system valve remain partially closed at normal cruise operation and regular required fuel is supplied.

The power enrichment / economizer system incorporate a valve operated varying opening jet as shown in figure below,

The valve get opened to supply rich mixture at full throttle operation. It regulates the additional fuel supply during the full throttle operation. The valve as shown is attached to the lever which operated by linking to throttle valve. Thus when full throttle operation the lever lifted and the opening to main jet fuel supply is increased and more fuel is supplied and thus increase the output power of engine.

This system does not interfere during cruising operation where economy mixture is supplied, it come in to role when more power is required at full throttle position, hence it is also known as power enrichment system.

3. Acceleration pump system –

In order to accelerate the vehicle, very rich mixture has to be supplied to the engine, and that richness of the mixture has to be obtained quickly and very rapidly.

For acceleration, if the throttle valve is suddenly opened there is a increase in the air flow, but due to inertia, liquid fuel flow does not increase in that proportion so there is a temporary lean mixture causing the engine to misfire and a temporary reduction in power output. To prevent this condition there are accelerating pump system incorporated in carburetor, as shown in figure below,

The pump comprises of a spring loaded plunger which takes care of the situation with the rapid opening of the throttle valve.

In crushing operation the cylinder get filled with fuel, when sudden acceleration, throttle movement link to actuator which pushes the plunger moves into the cylinder and forces an additional fuel at the venturi throat.

When the throttle is partly open the spring sets the plunger back, there is an arrangement which ensure that fuel in the pump cylinder is not forced through the jet when valve is slowly opened or leaks past the plunger.

Compensating devices used in modern carburetor :

Followings are the compensating devices normally used in modern carburetor,

1. Air-Bleed Jet –

Air-bleed jet compensating device contains an air-bleed into the main nozzle as shown in the figure given. The flow of air through this bleed is restricted by an orifice and thus it is called as restricted air-bleed jet.

When the engine is not operating the main jet and the air bleed jet will be filled with fuel. When the engine starts, initially the fuel starts coming through the main as well as the air-bleed jet. As the engine picks up, only air starts coming through the air bleed and mixes with fuel at main jet, making a air-fuel emulsion. This emulsion of air-liquid has negligible viscosity and surface tension. Thus same fuel-air mixture for the entire power range of operation.

If the fuel flow nozzle of the air-fuel system is placed in the centre of the venturi, both the air-bleed nozzle and the venturi are subjected to same engine suction resulting approximately same fuel-air mixture for the entire power range of operation.

2. Compensating Jet –

The compensating jet device make the mixture leaner as the throttle opens progressively. In this system additional compensating jet is incorporated, which is connected to the compensation well which is also vented to atmosphere like float chamber.

With the increase in air flow rate, there is decrease of fuel level in the compensating well, with decrease fuel supply through the compensating jet. The compensating jet thus progressively makes the mixture leaner as the main jet progressively makes the mixture richer.

The sum of the two, tends to keep the air-fuel mixture more or less constant. The main jet curve and the compensating jet curve are more or less reciprocal of each other, but the combined jet curve almost constant for entire power range.

3. Emulsion Tube –

The mixture correction is done by air bleeding in emulsion tube compensating device. In this, the main metering jet is kept at a level of about 25mm below the fuel level in the float chamber, so that it is also called as submerged jet.

The jet is located at the bottom of a well and the sides of the well have holes and these holes are in communication with the atmosphere as shown in given figure.

In the beginning the level of fuel in the float chamber and the well is the same. When the throttle is opened the pressure at the venturi throat decreases and fuel is drawn into the air stream. This result in progressively uncovering the holes in the central tube leading to increasing air-fuel ratio or decreasing richness of the mixture when all holes have been uncovered.

Normal flow takes place from the main jet. The air drawn through these holes in the well, and the fuel is emulsified and the pressure differential across the column of fuel is not as high as that in simple carburetor.

4. Back Suction Control / Pressure Reduction Method –

In back suction control compensating device, the top of the fuel float chamber is connected to air entry by means of a large vent line fitted with a control valve. Another line with a small orifice connects the top of the fuel float chamber with the venturi throat. With the control valve is completely open, the vent line is unrestricted and the pressure P_1 in the float chamber is atmospheric and the throat pressure will be P_2 . So the pressure differential acting on the orifice is $(P_1 - P_2)$.

If the valve is closed, the float chamber pressure will equalize with the pressure at the venturi throat and no fuel can flow. By proper adjustment of the control valve, the required pressure differential can be obtained in the float chamber. Thus altering the quantity of fuel discharge from the nozzle the required air fuel ratio mixture can be achieved. This is employed only in large carburetors.

5. Auxiliary Valve Method –

The arrangement of auxiliary valve is as shown in given figure.

When the engine is not operating the pressure P_1 acting on the top of the auxiliary valve is atmospheric. The vacuum at the venturi throat increases (the throat pressure P_2 decreases) with increase in load. This pressure differential $(P_1 - P_2)$ lifts the valve against the spring tension and more air is admitted and the mixture is prevented from becoming rich.

6. Auxiliary Port Method –

This arrangement consist an auxiliary port connecting choke valve section to throttle valve section as shown, and employed a butter fly valve in the passage of auxiliary port. If the butterfly valve is opened, additional air passes through this port reducing the flow of air through the venturi. This means that ΔP will be comparatively smaller. As a result fuel drawn is reduced. This method was popular for air-craft carburetor to compensate for the loss in density of air at high altitudes.

Expt. No. :

Title of Experiment : Study of Fuel Pump and Injector

Aim : To study Fuel Injection Systems, Fuel Injection Pumps and Fuel Injector.

Theory :

The fuel injection system is the most important part of the working of CI engines. The engine performance is greatly dependent on the effectiveness of the fuel injection system.

The injection system has to perform the important duty of initiating and controlling the combustion process of CI engines.

Requirement of Fuel Injection System

For proper running and good performance from the engine, the following requirements must be fulfilled by the injection system,

1. Accurate metering of the fuel injected per cycle – the quantity of the fuel metered should vary to meet changing speed and load requirements of the engine.
2. Proper control of rate of injection – to achieved desired heat release patter during combustion.
3. Accurate injection timing in the cycle – to ensure the maximum power output with clean burning and fuel economy.
4. Proper atomization of fuel and spray patter – to ensure very find droplet spray for rapid vaporization and mixing of fuel and air.
5. Uniform distribution of fuel droplets in the combustion chamber – to avoid rich mixture zone and abnormal combustion.
6. No lag during beginning and end of injection – to eliminate dribbling of fuel droplets into the cylinder.

Classification of Fuel Injection System :

Air Injection System -

In this system, fuel is forced into the cylinder by means of compressed air. It needs multistage compressor to supply compressed air at about 70 bar pressure and the fuel pump to draw the desired fuel from fuel tank. The mixture of compressed air and fuel is injected hence called as air injection system.

Advantages of Air Injection System –

1. It provides good atomization of fuel.
2. Heavy viscous fuels which are cheap can be used.
3. Fuel pump needs to develop only small pressure as injection assisted by high pressure compressed air.

Disadvantages of Air Injection System –

1. It can not be used for portable engine due to requirement of air compressor.
2. The compressor run from engine power, thus neat power output and mechanical efficiency get reduced.
3. Due to multistage compressor, the unit becomes bulky and expensive.
4. It needed separate maintenance of air compressor.

Airless / Solid Injection System -

In this system, fuel in liquid form is injected directly into the combustion chamber without any assistance of compressed air. Hence this system is called as airless or solid (not a mixture of air and fuel) injection system.

When the fuel is injected into combustion chamber at pressure about 70 bars helps it to atomized and form a fine spray which get vaporized by the high temperature of cylinder compressed air, and form air-fuel mixture.

1. Common Rail (CRDI-common rail direct injection) system –

In the common rail system a high pressure (HP) pump supplies fuel under high pressure to a fuel header. High pressure in the header forces the fuel to each of the nozzles located in the cylinders.

At the proper time push rod and rocker arm arrangement open valve and allow fuel to enter the respective cylinder through the nozzle. The pressure in the fuel header is maintained higher which enable fuel to get injected and spread in the combustion chamber.

The amount of fuel injected can be controlled by controlling the length of period of push rod stroke.

2. Individual Pump Injection system –

In this system each cylinder is provided with one pump and one injector. In this arrangement a separate metering and compression pump is provided for each cylinder. Fuel from tank is supplied to low pressure (LP) pump through which raises pressure to about 2.5bar and supplied to the fuel to individual high pressure (HP) pump of respective cylinder.

HP pumps increase the pressure to about 100 bar and above and meter the amount of fuel to be injected by the effective stroke of the plunger.

The HP pumps are placed close to the cylinder. The high pressure pump plunger is actuated by a cam and produces the fuel pressure necessary to open the injector valve at the correct time.

3. Distributor Injection system –

In this system the pump which pressurizes the fuel also meters and times it. The fuel pump after metering the required amount of fuel supplies it to a rotating distributor at the correct time for supply to each cylinder.

The number of injection strokes per cycle for the pump is equal to the number of cylinders. There is one metering element in each pump, a uniform distribution is ensured also cost of the fuel injection system is less than that of individual pump system.

4. Unit Injector system –

In the unit injector system the pump and the injector nozzle are combined in one housing and integrated as one unit.

Each cylinder is provided with one of these unit injectors. Fuel is brought up to the injector by a low pressure pump where at the proper time a rocker arm actuates the plunger and thus injects the fuel into the cylinder.

The amount of fuel injected is regulated by the effective stroke of the plunger.

Jerk Types of Fuel Pump :

The main function of fuel pump is to deliver accurately metered quantity of fuel under high pressure in the range of 100bar to 200 bar, at the correct instant to the injector. Bosch fuel pump is a jerk type pump which consist of a barrel in which a plunger reciprocates when driven by a camshaft. The plunger has a constant stroke and is single acting. The pump barrel has two radially opposite holes, one is inlet port and other is spill port.

During the delivery stroke a cam raises the plunger up against the plunger return spring. The plunger has vertical groove extended from top face of plunger to helix. When plunger at bottom of stroke barrel get filled by fuel through inlet port and up stroke of plunger when closes port then entrapped fuel get compressed by further plunger movement. The high pressure fuel then moves out from check valve by lifting it against spring and fuel is delivered to injector. As soon as helix groove open spill port the pressure get released and the check valve spring force to stop the delivery.

A rack and pinion arrangement is provided to rotate the plunger, thus the quantity of fuel delivered per stroke is regulated.

Fuel Injector :

Fuel injector atomize the fuel into very fine droplets it increase the surface are of the fuel droplets resulting in better mixing which ensure complete combustion. Atomization is done by forcing the fuel through a small orifice of nozzle under high pressure.

The fuel injector consist of following parts,

1. Needed valve
2. Compression spring

3. Nozzle
4. Injector body

The fuel from fuel pump is fed to the nozzle mouth through fuel passage, the fuel pressure acts on the nozzle valve which lifts it against the spring and allows the fuel to enter into the combustion chamber in the form of atomized spray through orifice.

Once the fuel from delivery pump gets exhausted, the spring tension pushes the nozzle valve back on its seat. To provide the lubrication between nozzle valve and its guide a small quantity of fuel is allowed to leak through the clearance and then drained back to the fuel tank through leak off port.

The adjusting screw provided on the top of spring house is used to adjust the spring tension and hence the valve opening pressure.

Conclusions :

1. We study the various types of fuel injection system, its different parts and working.
2. We study the jerk type fuel pump system, its construction, various parts and working.
3. We study the fuel injector system, its construction, various parts and its working.

Title of Experiment : Variable Load Test on Diesel Engine to Determine Various Efficiencies, BSFC and Heat Balance Sheet.

Aim : To determine Brake Power, Thermal Efficiency, Volumetric Efficiency, BSFC and to draw a Heat Balance Sheet.

Theory :

Energy supplied to an engine is the heat value of the fuel consumed. It has been repeatedly pointed out only part of this energy is transformed into useful work. The rest of its energy is either wasted or utilized in special applications like turbo compounding. The two main parts of the heat not available for work are the heat carried away by the exhaust gases and the cooling system.

To give sufficient data for preparation of a heat balance, a test should include a method of determining the power and the measurement of speed, load, fuel consumption, air-consumption, exhaust temperature, rate of flow of cooling water and its temperature rise while flowing through water jackets, Besides the small losses such as radiation and incomplete combustion, the above enumerated data makes it possible to account for the heat supplied by fuel and indicate its distribution.

It may be argued that some amount of frictional power is accounted in the rise of cooling water temperature and lubricating oil temperature etc. However, it is taken into account here to show that frictional losses also, include blow down and pumping losses and therefore it is not appropriate to put it in the heat balance. Since there are always certain losses which cannot be accounted, by including F.P in the heat balance, the unaccounted losses will reduce. Usually amount of heat carried by lubricating oil is comparatively small and are normally not included.

Engine Specifications :

1. Product Research Diesel Engine test setup.
2. Engine Type 1 cylinder, 4 stroke, water cooled.
3. Capacity = 661 cc.
4. Power = 3.5 KW.
5. Speed, N = 1500 rpm.
6. CR range from 12:1 to 18:1
7. Injection variation:0- 25 Deg bTDC
8. Dynamometer Type = Eddy current, water cooled, with loading unit
9. Software = EngineSoft 9_0 Engine performance analysis software

Procedure :

1. Check prime lubrication and fuel system.
2. Open inlet valve for cooling water and fuel supplying tank.
3. Ensure zero load on engine and fixed volume on burette.
4. Allow the engine to run at a certain speed after starting and then gradually load the engine by means of a loading system.
5. Note down all corresponding readings, and observations.
6. To stop the engine reduce the load gradually to zero and press engine stop knob / lever till engine spot completely.

Observations :

1. Stroke, $L = 110\text{mm}$.
2. Bore, $D = 87.5\text{ mm}$.
3. Dynamometer Arm = 0.185 m
4. Air Box Orifice Diameter, $d = 0.02\text{m}$
5. Air Box Coefficient of Discharge, $C_d = 0.6$
6. Density of Diesel Fuel = 830 Kg/m^3
7. Calorific Value of Diesel Fuel, $CV = 42000\text{ KJ/Kg}$.
8. Room Air Temperature, $T_{\text{room}} =$
9. Air Density at Room Temperature =

Observation Table : (take readings at least 3 different load conditions)

Sr. No.	Engine Load (Kg)	Engine Speed (rpm)	Mass of Cooling Water		Mass of Fuel Consumption	Manometer Reading (mm)	Brake Power (KW)	Temperature in °C						
			Engine (Lit. /Hr.)	Calorimeter (Lit. /Hr.)				T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	
1														
2														
3														
4														
5														

Calculations (Sample Calculation) :**1. Brake Thermal Efficiency :**

$$BP = \frac{2 \pi N T}{60 \times 1000} \text{ KJ/Sec}$$

2. Brake Thermal Efficiency :

$$\eta_{bth} = \frac{BP}{mf \times CV} \times 100$$

3. Brake Specific Fuel Consumption :

$$BSFC = \frac{mf}{BP} \text{ KJ/Kg} - \text{hr}$$

4. Volumetric Efficiency :

$$V_{act} = C_d \times A_o \times \sqrt{2 g h_a} \text{ in } m^3/sec$$

$$V_{swept} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{4} D^2 \times L \times \frac{N}{2}}{60} \text{ in } m^3/sec$$

$$\eta_{vol} = \frac{V_{act}}{V_{swept}} \times 100$$

5. Heat Balance Sheet on KJ/min basis : (on any one engine load condition)

3.1 Heat Supplied by Combustion of Fuel (Q_s) :

$$Q_s = m_f \times CV$$

3.2 Heat Equivalent to Brake Power (Q_{bp}) :

$$Q_{bp} = BP \times 60$$

3.3 Heat Carried Away by Cooling Water (Q_w) :

$$Q_w = m_w \times Cp_w \times (T_2 - T_1)$$

3.4 Heat Carried Away by Exhaust Gases (Q_g) :

$$Q_g = m_g \times Cp_g \times (T_5 - T_{room})$$

.....Heat Gain by Calorimeter water = Heat Lost by Exhaust Gases

$$m_{CW} \times Cp_{CW} \times (T_4 - T_1) = m_g \times Cp_g \times (T_6 - T_5)$$

$$m_g \times Cp_g = \underline{\hspace{2cm}}$$

3.5 Unaccounted Heat Loss (Q_{un}) :

$$Q_{un} = Q_s - (Q_{bp} + Q_w + Q_g)$$

Heat Supplied	KJ/min.	%	Heat Utilized	KJ/min.	%
Heat Supplied by Combustion of Fuel ($Q_s = m_f \times CV$)			1. Heat Equivalent to BP $Q_{bp} = BP \times 60$		
			2. Heat Carried Away by Cooling Water $Q_w = m_w \times Cp_w \times (T_2 - T_1)$		
			3. Heat Carried Away by Exhaust Gases $Q_g = m_g \times Cp_g \times (T_5 - T_{room})$		
			4. Unaccounted Heat Loss $Q_{un} = Q_s - (Q_{bp} + Q_w + Q_g)$		
Total Heat Supplied			Total Heat Utilized		

Result Table :

Sr. No.	Engine Load (Kg)	Engine Speed (rpm)	Brake Power (KW)	BSFC (Kg/KW-hr)	Volumetric Efficiency (%)	Brake Thermal Efficiency (%)	Exhaust Gas Temperature (°C)
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							

Conclusions :

- As engine load increases, the Brake Power and corresponding Specific Fuel Consumption increases.
- As engine load increases, the brake thermal efficiency, volumetric efficiency are increases.
- The heat balance sheet shows the heat supplied and heat utilized in various components.

Expt. No. : 03

Title of Experiment : Morse test on multi cylinder petrol engine for determination of friction power.

Aim : To study morse test on a 4-stroke, 3-cylinder Petrol Engine of its use in finding IP, BP, FP and mechanical efficiency.

Theory :

The Morse test consists of obtaining indicated power of engine without any elaborate equipment. The test consist of making in-operative, in turn, each cylinder of engine, and maintaining constant speed by reducing engine load and noting the reduction in brake power developed with the engine. Each cylinder is rendered inoperative by shorting the spark plug of the cylinder. It is assumed that pumping and friction losses are the same the cylinder is in operative as well as during firing. This test is applicable only to multi-cylinder petrol or diesel engines.

We Know, indicated power of engine is

$$IP = BP + FP$$

When all three cylinders are working, then power equation becomes,

$$(IP_1 + IP_2 + IP_3) = (BP_1 + BP_2 + BP_3) + (FP_1 + FP_2 + FP_3)$$

$$(IP_1 + IP_2 + IP_3) = BP_{All} + (FP_1 + FP_2 + FP_3) \dots \dots \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where,

$IP_1, IP_2, IP_3 =$ Indicated Power of cylinnder 1, 2 and 3

$BP_{All} =$ Total Brake Power when all cylinnder are working

$BP_1, BP_2, BP_3 =$ Brake Power of cylinnder 1, 2 and 3

$FP_1, FP_2, FP_3 =$ Friction Power of cylinnder 1, 2 and 3

When cylinders-1 is cut off, then power equation becomes,

$$(IP_2 + IP_3) = (BP_2 + BP_3) + (FP_1 + FP_2 + FP_3)$$

$$(IP_2 + IP_3) = BP_{cyl d-1 \text{ cut off}} + (FP_1 + FP_2 + FP_3) \dots \dots \text{Eq. 2}$$

On Subtracting Eq. 2 from Eq.1, we get,

$$(IP_1 + IP_2 + IP_3) - (IP_2 + IP_3) = (BP_{All} - BP_{cyl d-1 \text{ cut off}})$$

$$IP_1 = BP_{All} - BP_{cyl d-1 \text{ cut off}}$$

Similarly Indicated Power of cylinder-2 and cylinder-3 are,

$$IP_2 = BP_{All} - BP_{cyl d-2 \text{ cut off}}$$

$$IP_3 = BP_{All} - BP_{cylid-3\ cut\ off}$$

Thus, Total Indicated Power of engine is,

$$IP_{All} = IP_1 + IP_2 + IP_3$$

Hence the Friction of the engine is,

$$IP_{All} = BP_{All} + FP_{All}$$

$$FP_{Engine} = IP_{All} - BP_{All}$$

Engine Setup :

Engine Specifications :

1. No. of Cylinders = 3
2. No. of Strokes = 4
3. Fuel = Petrol
4. Rated Power = 27.6 KW @ 5000rpm
5. Cylinder Diameter = 66.5 mm
6. Stroke Length = 72 mm
7. Connecting Rod Length = 114 mm
8. Compression Ratio = 9.2 : 1
9. Orifice Diameter = 35 mm
10. Dynamometer Arm Length, R = 210 mm

Procedure :

1. Start water supply of for engine and calorimeter.
2. Before starting the engine check for fuel, lubrication oil and cooling water flow
3. Set the dynamometer to full load Condition
4. Start the engine and run for atleast 10 min. to attains the working temperature
5. Set the speed to certain value
6. Note down the speed and load on the engine when all cylinders are in working
7. Now cut off cylinder-1, speed of engine is dropped, maintain the speed by reducing the load on engine
8. Note down the readings of speed and load
9. Repeat the same for cut off cylinders in turns and note down all readings
10. After completion of experiment, remove engine load completely, bring back speed control knob to initial position and stop the engine
11. Continue cooling water supply atleast 30 min after engine stopped

Observations :

1. Fuel Density = 740 Kg/m³
2. Calorific Value of Fuel = 44000 KJ/Kg
3. Cooling water flow rate to engine = _____ LPH
4. Cooling water flow rate to calorimeter = _____ LPH
5. Room Temperature = _____ °C

Observation Table :

Sr. No.	Engine Working Condition	Engine Speed (rpm)	Engine Load (Kg)	Time for 100 ml Fuel Consumption (sec)
1	All Cyld. Working			
2	1 st Cyld. Cut off			
3	2 nd Cyld. Cut off			
4	3 rd Cyld. Cut off			

Sample Calculations :

1. Torque (T) Calculations :

When all cylinders are in working -

$$T_{all} = (W \times 9.81) \times R$$

$$T_{all} = \text{_____ Nm}$$

When Cylinder -1 is cut off (Cyld. 2 & 3 in working) -

$$T_{1-cut\ off} = (W_1 \times 9.81) \times R$$

$$T_{1-cut\ off} = \text{_____ Nm}$$

When Cylinder -2 is cut off (Cyld. 1 & 3 in working) -

$$T_{2-cut\ off} = (W_2 \times 9.81) \times R$$

$$T_{2-cut\ off} = \text{_____ Nm}$$

When Cylinder -3 is cut off (Cyld. 1 & 2 in working) -

$$T_{3-cut\ off} = (W_3 \times 9.81) \times R$$

$$T_{3-cut\ off} = \text{_____ Nm}$$

2. Brake Power (BP) Calculations :

When all cylinders are in working -

$$BP_{all} = (2 \pi N T_{all}) / 60$$

$$BP_{all} = \text{_____ KW}$$

When Cylinder -1 is cut off (Cyld. 2 & 3 in working) -

$$BP_{1-cut\ off} = (2 \pi N T_{1-cut\ off})/60$$

$$BP_{1-cut\ off} = \text{_____ } KW$$

When Cylinder -2 is cut off (Cyld. 1 & 3 in working) -

$$BP_{2-cut\ off} = (2 \pi N T_{2-cut\ off})/60$$

$$BP_{2-cut\ off} = \text{_____ } KW$$

When Cylinder -3 is cut off (Cyld. 1 & 2 in working) -

$$BP_{3-cut\ off} = (2 \pi N T_{3-cut\ off})/60$$

$$BP_{3-cut\ off} = \text{_____ } KW$$

3. Indicated Power (IP) Calculations :

When Cylinder -1 is cut off (Cyld. 2 & 3 in working) -

$$IP_1 = BP_{all} - BP_{1-cut\ off}$$

$$IP_1 = \text{_____ } KW$$

When Cylinder -2 is cut off (Cyld. 1 & 3 in working) -

$$IP_2 = BP_{all} - BP_{2-cut\ off}$$

$$IP_2 = \text{_____ } KW$$

When Cylinder -3 is cut off (Cyld. 1 & 2 in working) -

$$IP_3 = BP_{all} - BP_{3-cut\ off}$$

$$IP_3 = \text{_____ } KW$$

When all cylinders are in working -

$$IP_{all} = IP_1 + IP_2 + IP_3$$

$$IP_{all} = \text{_____ } KW$$

4. Friction Power (FP) Calculations :

$$FP_{Engine} = IP_{all} - BP_{all}$$

$$FP_{Engine} = \text{_____ } KW$$

5. Mechanical Efficiency (η_{mech}) Calculations :

$$\eta_{mech} = \frac{BP_{all}}{IP_{all}} \times 100$$

$$\eta_{mech} = \text{_____} \%$$

Result Table :

Sr. No.	Engine Working Condition	Engine Speed (rpm)	Engine Load (Kg)	Engine Torque (Nm)	Brake Power (KW)	Indicated Power (KW)	Friction Power (KW)	Mechanical Efficiency (%)
1	All Cyld. Working							
2	1 st Cyld. Cut off							
3	2 nd Cyld. Cut off							
4	3 rd Cyld. Cut off							

Conclusions :

From the data it is concluded that,

1. The Friction Power of an engine at _____ rpm speed is _____ KW
2. The Morse Test consist of running the engine against a dynamometer at a particular speed, cutting out each cylinder in turn and noting the fall in Brake Power while maintaining speed constant.
3. When one cylinder is cut off, the power developed is reduced and speed is falls

Expt. No. :

Title of Experiment : Study of Ignition System.

Aim : To study various parts, construction and working of the different ignition systems used in SI engine.

Battery Ignition System :

Most of the modern spark-ignition engine use battery ignition system. The required components of the system are, battery of 6 volt or 12 volt, induction coil, contact breaker, condenser, distributor and spark plug.

Battery is connected to the primary of the induction coil through starting switch, other end of the primary coil is connected to the breaker and through it to the ground. When breaker contact points are closed, as one terminal of the battery is grounded, the circuit is closed by passing the current from the battery - starting switch - primary coil - contact breaker - ground and back to the battery.

Thus the primary circuit is closed, a current is flow through the primary coil and magnetize core of the coil. The emf is induced in the secondary but this is not sufficient to produce a spark at the spark plug.

When primary circuit is opened due to separation of contact breaker points, the magnetic field collapses, the emf induced in the secondary coil, which is directly proportional to the rate at which the magnetic field collapse. A capacitor is connected across the contact breaker helps to collapse the field very rapidly by absorbing part of the energy of the magnetic field which is thrown back into the primary winding and produces a very high voltage in the secondary. This emf in the secondary coil is sufficient to ignite the charge is supply to respective spark plug with the help of distributor.

Ballast resistor is made of iron wire, it having property that its electrical resistance increases very rapidly if a certain temperature is exceed. When engine runs for a long time at low speed then induction coil get overheated, thus as ballast coil exceed its temperature, its resistance increases very rapidly and the primary circuit current reduces to safe value. In cold condition ballast resistance not come in to play hence more current flow in the primary circuit.

Advantages of Battery Ignition Systems –

1. Its initial cost is low compared with magneto.
2. It provides better sparks at low speeds of the engine during starting and idling.
3. The maintenance cost is negligible except the battery.
4. The spark efficiency remains unaffected by advance and retard positions of the timing control mechanism.
5. The simplicity of the distributor drive.

Disadvantages of Battery Ignition Systems –

1. The engine can not be started if the battery runs down.
2. The weight of the battery ignition system is greater than magneto.
3. The wiring involved in the coil ignition is more complicated than that used in magneto, hence it more likelihood of defects occurring in the system.
4. The sparking voltage drops with increasing speed of the engine.

Magneto Ignition System :

Magneto ignition system, has its own electric generator to provide the necessary energy for the system., and thus it does not required battery, also it replaces ignition coil.

The figure shows rotating magnet type magneto ignition system, in this a rotating magnet attached to the cam which controls the opening and closing of the contact breaker. The primary and secondary winding are kept stationary, one end of both are grounded and other end of primary winding is grounded through the contact breaker, a capacity is attached in parallel to the contact breaker.

The rotating magnet is rotated by engine, thus it producing a voltage in primary winding, the circuit is completed through contact breaker, during this capacitor get charged. A current is flow through the primary coil and magnetize core. The emf is induced in the secondary but this is not sufficient to produce a spark at the spark plug.

When primary circuit is opened due to separation of contact breaker points, the magnetic field collapses, the emf induced in the secondary coil, which is directly proportional to the rate at which the magnetic field collapse. A capacitor is connected across the contact breaker helps to collapse the field very rapidly by absorbing part of the energy of the magnetic field which is thrown back into the primary winding and produces a very high voltage in the secondary. This emf in the secondary coil is sufficient to ignite the charge is supply to respective spark plug with the help of distributor.

Advantages of Magneto Ignition Systems –

1. It does not required battery and ignition coil, hence corresponding cost is reduced.
2. With the increase in speed the current generated also increased, thus it gives strong spark, therefore it is used in racing cars and aero-plane.
3. It having light weight, occupies less space and less maintenance, thus it is favored in two wheelers.
4. It is more reliable as the complicated ignition coil and battery run down problems are not there.

Disadvantages of Magneto Ignition Systems –

1. Since wiring carry high voltage current, there is a strong possibility of leakage which may cause.
2. This system required extensive shielding to prevent leakage of high voltage current.
3. At low speed, it develops poor quality of spark at the time of starting, thus some time separate battery is needed for starting.

Electronic Ignition System [Transistorized Coil Ignition (TCI) System or Transistor Assisted Contact (TAC) System] :

A transistor is used in replacement for the breaker points and condenser of conventional ignition system. As shown in figure, the emitter (E) of the transistor is connected to igniting coil through a ballast resistor and the collector (C) to the battery. When the cam operated contact point opens the base current and thereby, the primary circuit current is interrupted and normal induction coil operation follows.

The current through the contact breaker is reduced by a larger amount due to the fact that the contact breaker has to switch only the base current of the transistor this improves the life of the contact breaker. The inductance of the primary coil is also reduced which allows quicker current build-up. More energy can be stored in the coil because the coil current is not limited by the breaker contact.

The contact points can be made lighter to reduce contact bounce, it reduces wear of contact points ensures that the system output will not decrease with time. These results in higher accuracy and less need for maintenance.

Advantages of TCI Systems –

1. Higher ignition voltage and a long duration of spark.
2. Reduced wear of contact breaker points.
3. Consistency of spark voltage over the engine speed range.
4. Increased dwell and less contact bounce.

Disadvantages of TCI Systems –

1. System requires the contact breaker points of the conventional system for timing the spark, however, the wear of contact breaker points is reduced due to low breaker current.
2. The maximum speed of engine is governed by the limitations of contact breaker mechanism.

Conclusions :

From the study experiment it is concluded that,

1. The Electronics Ignition System is more efficient and advance as compared to Battery Ignition and Magneto Ignition system and hence it is now a day used is almost all vehicles.
2. Here we study the various types of ignition system and their working.

Pimpri Chinchwad Education Trust's
Pimpri Chinchwad College of Engineering & Research, Ravet

Department of Mechanical Engineering
Lab Manual : Applied Thermodynamics

Expt. No. :

Title of Experiment : Test on Positive Displacement Air Compressor

Aim : To determine Isothermal Efficiency and Volumetric Efficiency of the two-stage compressor.

Theory :

Compressed air has found many applications in now-a-days life, right from inflating automobile types to driving pneumatic circuits and tools. Generally, compression process found in single stage compressors in polytropic process, in which $P V^n = C$. For air, value of n is between 1 to 1.4. For $n = 1$, compression is isothermal, which is desired, but practically it is not possible, Isothermal compression gives lesser work requirement and cool working of the compressor. Several means are adopted for the compression process to become as near as possible to isothermal, like cooling of cylinder, cold water spray in cylinder or multistage compression.

In two stage compression, air is partially compressed in low pressure cylinder. This air is passed through cooler between first stage and second stage so that air at inlet of second stage is at lower temperature than first stage outlet. Final compression is completed in second stage. Additionally, cylinders are also provided with fins for cooling. This system helps to lower the value of Polytropic index 'n'. Also, as the compressors are provided with clearance volume, two stage compressors can achieve higher volumetric efficiency than single stage compressors, because of lower compression ratio per stage. This effect is more pronounced at higher delivery pressures.

The apparatus consists of a two stage air compressor with intercooler driven by an induction motor. It sucks air from inlet air tank through an orifice and air filter. Compressed air from first stage goes to finned intercooler, where its temperature is lowered and it enters the second stage cylinder. Final compression is completed here and air is then sending to the air receiver. For forcing the air over the fins, a fan is mounted over the compressor pulley.

Schematic Diagram of Experimental Setup :

P_1 = Ambient pressure

P_3 = Gauge pressure After HP cylinder

T_1 = Ambient Temperature

T_3 = Temperature before HP cylinder

h_w = Manometer reading

P_2 = Gauge pressure after LP cylinder

P_4 = Tank pressure

T_2 = Temperature after LP cylinder

T_4 = Temperature after HP cylinder

RPM = Compressor speed

Precautions :

1. Always check for proper water level in manometer and oil level in compressor before starting the compressor.
2. Proper earthing is necessary for the equipment.
3. Do not temper with settings of pressure relief valve and pressure switch.
4. Run the compressor at least 5 minutes a week.
5. Replace compressor oil every 100 hrs. of operation.
6. Never obstruct the orifice while compressor is working as it will suck the manometer water.
7. Drain the water collected in receiver every 10 hrs. of operation.

Specifications :

1. Bore diameter of LP cylinder = 70mm
2. Bore diameter of HP cylinder = 62.5mm
3. Stroke length of LP & HP cylinder = 56.5mm
4. Orifice diameter = 10mm

Procedure :

1. Start the mains indicator of the panel, check that all indicators are in working position.
2. When we start the mains On/Off then temperature indicator, wattmeter, RPM indicator will starts glowing.
3. Now start the compressor and close delivery valve of the compressor and start the compressor.
4. Let the receiver pressure rise up to around 2.5 Kg/cm^2 , now open the delivery valve so that constant delivery pressure of 2 Kg/cm^2 is achieved.
5. Wait for some time and see that delivery pressure remains constant. Note down the observations and complete the observation table.
6. Now close the delivery valve and let pressure rise to about 4.5 Kg/cm^2 . Open the delivery valve and adjust delivery pressure to 4 Kg/cm^2
7. Note down all the observations.
8. Repeat the same procedure for different delivery pressures.

Observation Table :

Sr. No.	P1 (Kg/cm ²)	P2 (Kg/cm ²)	P3 (Kg/cm ²)	P4 (Kg/cm ²)	T1 (°C)	T2 (°C)	T3 (°C)	T4 (°C)	h _w (mm)	N (RPM)	Energy Reading (KW)
1											
2											
3											
4											

Sample Calculations :

1. Density of Air (ρ_a) –

Using gas equation, $P_1 \times V_1 = m_a \times R \times T_1$

$$m_a = \frac{P_1 \times V_1}{R \times T_1}$$

$$\rho_a = \frac{m_a}{V_1} = \frac{\left(\frac{P_1 \times V_1}{R \times T_1}\right)}{V_1}$$

$$\rho_a = \frac{P_1}{R \times T_1} \quad \dots \quad P_1 \text{ in } \frac{N}{m^2} \quad \text{and } T_1 \text{ in Kelvin}$$

$$\rho_a = \text{_____ } Kg/m^3$$

2. Manometer head in terms of column of air (h_a) –

$$h_a = \frac{h_w \rho_w}{\rho_a} \quad \dots \dots h_w \text{ in meter}$$

$$h_a = \text{_____ } \text{meter of air column}$$

3. Actual air delivered –

Volume of air delivered in m^3/sec is,

$$V_a = C_d A_o \sqrt{2 g h_a}$$

$$V_a = C_d \left(\frac{\pi}{4} d_o^2\right) \sqrt{2 g h_a} \quad \dots \dots C_d = \text{Coeff. of Discharge} = 0.66$$

$$\dots \dots d_o = \text{Orifice diameter} = 0.01m$$

$$V_a = \text{_____ } m^3/sec$$

Mass of air delivered in Kg/sec is,

$$m_a = \rho_a V_a$$

$$m_a = \text{_____ } Kg/sec$$

4. Volumetric Efficiency (η_{vol}) –

$$\eta_{vol} = \frac{\text{Actual Volume of Air Delivered}}{\text{Displacement of Piston}}$$

$$\eta_{vol} = \frac{V_a}{\left(\frac{\pi}{4} D_{LP}^2 L\right) \frac{N}{60}} \quad \dots \dots D_{LP} = \text{Bore diameter of LP cylinder}$$

$$\eta_{vol} = \text{_____ } \%$$

5. Polytrophic Index (n) and work done in each stage of compressor–

For LP cylinder compression : Stage – I

$$\frac{T_1}{T_2} = \left(\frac{P_1}{P_2}\right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}}$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{T_1}{T_2}\right) = \frac{n-1}{n} \ln\left(\frac{P_1}{P_2}\right)$$

$$\frac{n-1}{n} = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{T_1}{T_2}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{P_1}{P_2}\right)} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{n}{n-1} = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_1}{P_2}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{T_1}{T_2}\right)}$$

$$\frac{n-1}{n} = \text{_____} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{n}{n-1} = \text{_____}$$

$$WD_{LP} = \frac{n}{n-1} m_a R T_1 \left[\left(\frac{P_2}{P_1}\right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} - 1 \right]$$

$$WD_{LP} = \text{_____} \text{ watt}$$

For HP cylinder compression : Stage – II

$$\frac{T_3}{T_4} = \left(\frac{P_2}{P_3}\right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}}$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{T_3}{T_4}\right) = \frac{n-1}{n} \ln\left(\frac{P_2}{P_3}\right)$$

$$\frac{n-1}{n} = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{T_3}{T_4}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{P_2}{P_3}\right)} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{n}{n-1} = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_2}{P_3}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{T_3}{T_4}\right)}$$

$$\frac{n-1}{n} = \text{_____} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{n}{n-1} = \text{_____}$$

$$WD_{HP} = \frac{n}{n-1} m_a R T_3 \left[\left(\frac{P_3}{P_2}\right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} - 1 \right]$$

$$WD_{HP} = \text{_____} \text{ watt}$$

Hence, Actual total compressor work done is,

$$WD_{act} = WD_{LP} + WD_{HP}$$

$$WD_{act} = \text{_____} \text{ watt}$$

6. Isothermal Work done –

$$WD_{iso} = m_a R T_1 \ln\left(\frac{P_3}{P_1}\right)$$

$$WD_{iso} = \text{_____ watt}$$

7. Isothermal Efficiency (η_{iso}) –

$$\eta_{iso} = \frac{WD_{iso}}{WD_{act}}$$

$$\eta_{iso} = \text{_____ \%}$$

Result Table :

Sr. No.	Delivery Pressure (Kg/cm ²)	Volumetric Efficiency (%)	Isothermal Efficiency (%)
1			
2			
3			
4			

Conclusions :

1. With increase in delivery pressure, there is _____ in volumetric efficiency.
2. With increase in delivery pressure, there is _____ in isothermal efficiency.

Graphs :

1. Delivery pressure on x-axis and volumetric efficiency on y-axis.
2. Delivery pressure on x-axis and isothermal efficiency on y-axis.

Pimpri Chinchwad Education Trust's
Pimpri Chinchwad College of Engineering & Research, Ravet

Department of Mechanical Engineering
Lab Manual : Applied Thermodynamics

Expt. No. :

Title of Experiment : Assignment on Alternative fuels used in IC engines.

Aim : To study the need of alternative fuels and various alternative available and their prospectus as alternative fuel in IC engines.

Introduction : (current scenario of conventional fuel like petrol and diesel in auto sector, pollution impact of conventional fuel and need of alternative fuel to automobile and so on.)

Alternative Fuels : (it includes : what is alternative fuel, potential and future of alternative fuel, Indian biofuel policy and biofuel scenario etc.)

Liquid Alternative Fuels – (brief description, applications, images, properties etc.)

- Alcohol
- Methanol
- Ethanol
- Vegetable Oil
- Bio Diesel

Gaseous Alternative Fuels – (brief description, applications, images, properties etc.)

- Hydrogen
- CNG – Compressed Natural Gas
- LPG – Liquefied Natural Gas

Electric Vehicles – (brief description, applications, images, properties etc.)

Note :

1. Assignment must be in brief.
2. To complete above assignment use WHO data, Indian biofuel policy report, various published papers and information available on internet and books etc.

Prof. Rahul Krishnaji Bawane (Lab In-Charge)

Asst. Prof. Mechanical Engg. Dept., PCCOER

Page 1 of 1

Pimpri Chinchwad Education Trust's
Pimpri Chinchwad College of Engineering & Research, Ravet

Department of Mechanical Engineering
Lab Manual : Applied Thermodynamics

Expt. No. :

Title of Experiment : Visit Report to Automobile Service Station.

Aim : To study and bridge the gap between theory and practical knowledge by Service Station Visit, also to upgrade recent development and maintenance technology available in market.

Template for Visit to Service Workshop

Samarth Automobile Workshop,
Laxminagar, Ravet, Pune - 412101

Date of Visit : _____

Visit : Under Academic Syllabus of subject Applied Thermodynamics SE Mechanical (sem.-II) :
Practical No. 8 -Visit to Automobile Service Station.

Details of Samarth Automobile – Hyundai Car Service Station :

1. Organization Chart :

Prof. Rahul Krishnaji Bawane (Lab In-Charge)

Asst. Prof. Mechanical Engg. Dept., PCCOER

2. Cars Models Serviced : Some Car Models with Specification

Car Model		Specifications	
Maruti Swift		Overall Length	3850 mm
		Overall Width	1695 mm
		Overall Height	1530 mm
		Power	87ps @ 6000 rpm
		Torque	114 Nm @ 4000 rpm
		No. of Cylinders	4 Cyld.
		Displacement	1197 cc
Maruti Alto 800		Overall Length	3395 mm
		Overall Width	1490 mm
		Overall Height	1475 mm
		Power	48ps @ 6000 rpm
		Torque	69 Nm @ 3500 rpm
		No. of Cylinders	3 Cyld.
		Displacement	796 cc
<p style="text-align: center;">Atleast any 10 Car models and their specification</p>			

3. Service Shop Flow Chart :

4. Body Shop Flow Chart :

5. General Servicing Scheduled :

Servicing No.	On basis of KM running	On basis of Months
Free Servicing - 1	1000 Km	1 Months
Free Servicing - 2	5000 Km	6 Months
Free Servicing - 3	10000 Km	12 Months
Paid Servicing - 1	20000 Km	24 Months
Paid Servicing - 2	30000 Km	36 Months
Paid Servicing - 3	As per vehicle condition	As per vehicle condition

6. Some Road Safety Signs : (paste color print)

7. Visit Photos :

Visit Observations :

1. **Scissor Lift :** (write brief description on the basis of information available on internet and visit experience)

2. **Wheel Alignment :** (write brief description on the basis of information available on internet and visit experience)

3. Wheel Balancing : (write brief description on the basis of information available on internet and visit experience)

4. Other types of Regular Maintenance work and its procedure (at least any 3)

Job Card :

Repair Order		TAG No : 1																																																												
Samarth Automobiles(W2540) HYUNDAI <small>NEW THINKING. NEW POSSIBILITIES.</small>		Ravet Pune-412101 Sr No 108. Opp SB Patil School PUNE Tel : 918698859450 Fax : 918698859450 GST No. : 27CCJPS8641A1ZF e-mail : samarthhyundai@gmail																																																												
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Promise Date : 22.02.2020 06:30 Delivery Time : Service Advisor : SAGAR PATIL Mobile No : Est. Amount : ₹ 0 Preferred Mode of contact : Call <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SMS <input type="checkbox"/> E-Mail <input type="checkbox"/> I hereby authorize for the Repair to be executed using necessary materials and I am affixing my signature below in evidence of agreeing terms & condition given in the Annexure A of the repair Customer Signature	 C-Crack P-Peeling, D-Dent/Damage, S-Scratch/Spot, R-Rust	<table border="1" style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="4" style="text-align: center;">Fuel Gauge</th> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2" style="text-align: left;">E</th> <th colspan="2" style="text-align: right;">F</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Service Book</td> <td>Yes/No</td> <td>Rear View Mirro</td> <td>Yes/No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tool Kit</td> <td>Yes/No</td> <td>IDO</td> <td>Yes/No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Spare Wheel</td> <td>Yes/No</td> <td>Wheel Cover</td> <td>Yes/No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Jack</td> <td>Yes/No</td> <td>Mud Flaps</td> <td>Yes/No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Jack Handle</td> <td>Yes/No</td> <td>Mats</td> <td>Yes/No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Car Perfume</td> <td>Yes/No</td> <td>Dicky Mat</td> <td>Yes/No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Clock</td> <td>Yes/No</td> <td>Speaker FR</td> <td>Yes/No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Stereo</td> <td>Yes/No</td> <td>Speaker FR</td> <td>Yes/No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CD Player</td> <td>Yes/No</td> <td>Tweeters</td> <td>Yes/No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mouth Piece</td> <td>Yes/No</td> <td>SD Card</td> <td>Yes/No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Cigrate Lighter</td> <td>Yes/No</td> <td>Antenna</td> <td>Yes/No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Battery name</td> <td></td> <td>Battery S.no:</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tire maker</td> <td></td> <td>Tire No:</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> I hereby certify that the repair s have been carried out to my entire satisfaction Customer Signature	Fuel Gauge				E		F		Service Book	Yes/No	Rear View Mirro	Yes/No	Tool Kit	Yes/No	IDO	Yes/No	Spare Wheel	Yes/No	Wheel Cover	Yes/No	Jack	Yes/No	Mud Flaps	Yes/No	Jack Handle	Yes/No	Mats	Yes/No	Car Perfume	Yes/No	Dicky Mat	Yes/No	Clock	Yes/No	Speaker FR	Yes/No	Stereo	Yes/No	Speaker FR	Yes/No	CD Player	Yes/No	Tweeters	Yes/No	Mouth Piece	Yes/No	SD Card	Yes/No	Cigrate Lighter	Yes/No	Antenna	Yes/No	Battery name		Battery S.no:		Tire maker		Tire No:	
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Time		Signature																																																												
Last Visit : 27/12/2018 , 52421 Km, Paid Service , W2406 , R201815398 , ₹ 17797.98																																																														
Last Visit 3rd Day PSF Rating :																																																														
Deferred Job (Last Visit) : null																																																														

R Replaced **T** Top-Upped **C** Checked/Cleaned **A** Adjusted/Tightened

RO NO : R202000076 RO DATE : 22/02/2020 WORK TYPE : Paid Service SA : SAGAR PATIL

Job Description

1	Free/Paid Service Jobs	1. Engine Oil R/T/C	2. Oil filter R/C	3. Transmission Oil R/T/C	Tech:			
		4. Spark Plug R/T/C	5. Air Filter R/C	6. Brake Fuel R/T/C	7. A/T Transmission Oil R/T/C	8. Clutch Fluid R/T/C		
2	Misc. Jobs	9. Coolant R/T/C	10. Fuel Filter R/C	11. Timing Belt R/C/A	12. A/C Belt R/C/A	13. Coolant Pump Belt R/C/A		
		14. Power Steering Belt R/T/C	15. Check all hoses <input type="checkbox"/>	16. Throttle Body Clean <input type="checkbox"/>	17. Check Brake/Clutch <input type="checkbox"/>	18. Brake/Clutch Pedal Play <input type="checkbox"/>		
		1. Wheel Balancing <input type="checkbox"/>	2. Tyre Rotation <input type="checkbox"/>	3. Check Tyre pressure <input type="checkbox"/>	4. Check any leakage (Engine, T/m, P/Stg.) <input type="checkbox"/>	5. Hi Scan <input type="checkbox"/>		
		6. Check Headlight <input type="checkbox"/>	7. Check Traillight <input type="checkbox"/>	8. Check Dashboard light/combination switch <input type="checkbox"/>	9. Check other lights <input type="checkbox"/>	10. Check Drive Shaft/Steering boot <input type="checkbox"/>		
		11. Check Under Body <input type="checkbox"/>	12. Check Struts/Shock Absorbers For leakage <input type="checkbox"/>	13. Battery terminal fluid level and tightness <input type="checkbox"/>	14. Fuel Injector R/C	15. check wiper & w/z washer operation <input type="checkbox"/>		
		16. Check W/S washer nozzle Spray <input type="checkbox"/>	17. Check water in W/S washer bottle <input type="checkbox"/>	18. Next Service due/ERS Sticker <input type="checkbox"/>	19. Service Book Entry <input type="checkbox"/>	20. Wheel not Check <input type="checkbox"/>		
		21. Wheel Alignment <input type="checkbox"/>						Tech :
		22. Check A/C Operation <input type="checkbox"/>	Cut in Temp.:		Cut in Temp.:		Tech :	
		A/C Gas recovery done <input type="checkbox"/>	A/C Gas Charging done <input type="checkbox"/>	Remarks:				

Brake Inspection (Thickness)								Tyre Inspection					
Front LH		Front RT		Rear LH		Rear RT		Tyre	Front LH	Front RT	Rear LH	Rear RT	Spare Wheel
PAD	DISC	PAD	DISC	PAD Shoe	DISC Drum	PAD Shoe	DISC Drum	Depth					
Min. Vs Actual		Min. Vs Actual		Min. Vs Actual		Min. Vs Actual		Pressure					
								Damage	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No

4	Free/Paid Service Jobs	1.	Tech:					
		2.	Alloted Time(By Floor I/C):					
		3.	Start Time(By Tech.):					
		4.	End Time(By Tech.):					
		5.	6.					

5	Electrician	Battery Check	Cell	1	2	3	4	5	6	Elect. Name:				
		Top up	Sp. Gravity								Start Time(By Tech):			
		Alternator Charging Voltage									End Time(By Tech):			
With Out Load:				With Load:										

6	Door Adjustment	1. Check All Doors <input type="checkbox"/>	2. Check All Door Locks <input type="checkbox"/>	3. Check All Window Glass Operation <input type="checkbox"/>	Denter Name: Start			
		4. Check Hood & Tailgate Operation <input type="checkbox"/>	5. <input type="checkbox"/>	6. <input type="checkbox"/>	Time (By)		End Time (By Tech):	

7 Technician Remarks Warranty (If any):

WASHING ROAD TEST Remarks:

PARTS CONFIRMED FINAL NSP. Remarks:

If vehicle likely to be Delayed, Revised Delivery Date / Time:

Customer Informed Date / Time: Actual Vehicle Ready Date / Time:

No.	Labour Description	Amount	No.	Labour Description	Amount
1.			8.		
2.			9.		
3.			10.		
4.			11.		
5.			12.		
6.			13.		
7.			14.		

Signature Part Supervisor Final Inspection Floor I/C Server Advisor Washing Supervisor

Conclusion : (based on visit experience)

Prof. Rahul Krishnaji Bawane (Lab In-Charge)
Asst. Prof. Mechanical Engg. Dept., PCCOER